

"Grey matters: Integrating Grey Literature and Mainstream Media Mentions into Scientometric Analysis"

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This study describes a proof of concept for the integration of grey literature and, more specifically, mainstream media mentions of academic researchers within scientometric and bibliometric analyses. The Python pipeline automatically and on a large scale harvests, contextualizes, and evaluates researchers' mentions in mainstream media against their academic activities. Merging data from FRIS, OpenAlex, and Belga.Press databases, we developed a methodology to discern mentions related to genuine research from academic expertise or those mentions driven by a researcher's non-academic activities. A scoring is assigned for each mention to differentiate between research-specific and more general expertise. In the process, each step is logged, traceable, and fully transparent, compliant with the push towards Open Science. This approach enhances the understanding of a researcher's public visibility and equally contributes to more informed assessments of research impact, paving the way for more refined metrics in academic evaluations.

Introduction

Grey literature refers to a broad spectrum of non-academic publications beyond traditional scholarly publishing. Grey literature, spans policy documents, media reports, social media content, government reports, working papers, dissertations, conference proceedings, technical specifications or even data standards. Unlike peer-reviewed academic literature, grey literature does not undergo formal validation through peer review processes. Instead, it thrives on the often fast-paced (Cooper et al., 2019) provision of unstructured information that cater various audiences, serving as technical documentation, knowledge adoption or science communication. Its significance lies in its ability to offer information and perspectives not readily accessible through conventional academic channels (Imran et al., 2019; Schöpfel, 2019).

Although their significance (Gul et al., 2020) and assessment (M. S. Bickley et al., 2020; Hovden, 2013; Myohanen et al., 2005; Wani & Ganaie, 2022) in the academic publishing value chain is still being debated, grey literature is increasingly endorsed by funding agencies and academic institutions (Joubert & Weingart, 2019; McDevitt, 2022; Medina, 2023). Where traditional academic resources maintain their central position in academic communication, grey literature does play a pivotal role in spreading research findings, communication of technical solutions, and documentation of recent research.

A specific subset of grey literature, mainstream media mentions, has been less the centre of attention yet equally includes a wide variety of scientific domains, with a small subset of academics achieving high visibility in mainstream media content (Jonker et al., 2022), yet the correlation between mainstream media mentions and academic citations remain largely unclear (Anderson et al., 2020; Leidecker-Sandmann et al., 2023). Nonetheless, some scientists proactively manage media interactions for strategic aims (adoption), others shape their

communication strategies based on existing media narratives (adaptation) (Moorhead et al., 2023; Olesk, 2021).

This dynamic illustrates not only the varied approaches scientists take to engage with media, but also the potential challenges and opportunities that such interactions present for the integration of these interactions in traditional bibliometric indicators. One of those challenges is harvesting media mentions of researchers, assess whether the mentions are related to their research (or rather to their relative celebrity status (Fahy, 2015)) and weighing their relevance within the broader debate. The lack of formal citation practices and the very nature of unstructured data makes it difficult to track its impact and credit its authors. A variety of initiatives have been undertaken to incorporate grey literature within institutional repositories (Gelfand, 2005; Lambert et al., 2006; Schoepfel et al., 2012; Schoepfel & Stock, 2008), ranging from ingestion of grey literature in institutional repositories, or even dedicated grey literature repositories such as the ‘Grey Literature Report’ and OpenGrey to more domain specific warehouses such as ArXiv or catch-all repositories such as Zenodo. Mentions in mainstream media often fall, again, out of scope of these repositories for the lack of an efficient method of harvesting detailed observations of mainstream media mentions.

Given grey literature's role in the scientific research value chain and the growing acknowledgement of the value of the interplay between mainstream media and research, alternative methods should be applied to incorporate their 'impact' in scientometrics and bibliometrics. Some effort is put into harvesting references in grey literature (M. Bickley et al., 2022; M. S. Bickley et al., 2020) or linking mainstream media articles to scientific research (Ravenscroft et al., 2018; Wang & Yu, 2021) or even harvesting mainstream media mentions (Federico et al., 2003), a granular automated harvesting has not been built. Finally, mentions of a researcher in media articles may reflect rather their status as a public figure than their expertise or specific research contributions, highlighting the need to distinguish between mentions that are genuinely related to their academic research and those that are mentioned primarily due to their celebrity status with little or no connection to their actual research activities.

Research goals

The goal of the research is to build a proof of concept (1) retrieving mentions of authors in mainstream media articles on a large scale, (2) identifying whether the media presence is related to their academic research, (3) defining to what extent the mention is related to research or more general about domain expertise and (4) enabling provenance of each step by locating the specific sentences in which researchers are mentioned. This granular harvesting of mainstream media mentions is crucial for further analysis on the dynamics between researchers and mainstream media, both for including these mentions on bibliometric analysis as for contextualization of these mentions.

Data Set

We merged data from three distinct databases—FRIS, OpenAlex, and Belga.Press, resulting in the linkage of a comprehensive list of researchers, their scholarly expertise, and their mainstream media mentions.

Belga.press

Mainstream media articles were pulled from the Belga.Press database. This database aggregates content from major Belgian news brands containing over 20 million articles. This vast dataset was, for computational reasons, reduced querying the database with terms of a custom-built Dutch lexicon. The lexicon listed terms associated with university and research related in combination with words associated with the Middle Ages (see section ‘limitations’). The selection of terms associated with the Middle Ages was strategic to enhance the likelihood of identifying articles relevant to academic research in this domain. In Dutch, the Middle Ages (cf. *middeleeuwen*) notably is a domain where synonyms and hyponyms are scarce. Considering the occasional pejorative use of the term ‘Middle Ages’. allowed us to maintain a

sufficient level of 'noise' within the data. This approach maximizes the discovery of academic mentions while preserving a broad spectrum of articles, thusly reducing a potential bias.

An initial lexicon was extended using similar terms as pulled through the Dutch NLTK and WordNet libraries (synonyms, hypernyms, and hyponyms). Each article with one of the terms of the extended lexical list in either the title or the body of the text was selected and added to the to be processed mainstream media dataset.

FRIS database

For our comprehensive list of researcher's names, we limited the researchers to those listed on the FRIS database, a comprehensive resource holding over 55,000 research projects, 40,000 researchers, and 560,000 scientific publications, along with recent additions of patents, datasets, and research infrastructure information (accessible via www.researchportal.be). We pulled data from the FRIS database on June 23, 2023, and queried the database over the APIs extracting a snapshot of listed researchers on FRIS (see section 'limitations').

OpenAlex

Though FRIS is the go-to database for an extensive and updated list of researchers in Flanders, this database does not hold information about the expertise or research topics of the researchers. To relate topics or expertise, we matched each researcher from the FRIS database with their respective identifiers (e.g. ORCIDs) within the OpenAlex database. OpenAlex is an open science repository and serves as a comprehensive catalog of scholarly outputs. OpenAlex dataset stores traditional metadata about the academic output—including titles, abstracts, and in many cases, full texts, harvesting data from a wide variety of sources, including but not limited to Crossref, ORCID, ROR, DOAJ, Unpaywall, PubMed, PubMed Central, Zenodo and others.

Names in FRIS without corresponding data in OpenAlex were excluded from the research, for the pipeline relies on harvesting topics from OpenAlex linked to individual researchers (see section 'limitations').

Python pipeline overview

A python pipeline was developed to be scalable and efficient, avoiding computationally intensive tools such as large language models. Instead, the approach deploys zero-shot named entity recognition (NER), zero-shot coreference resolution libraries and topic similarity. Such zero-shot libraries are particularly interesting for they allow transposing successful pipelines onto novel data sets with limited code rewriting nor elaborate fine-tuning.

Querying the Belga.Press data set

The Python pipeline was developed to correlate data across the FRIS, Belga.Press, and OpenAlex databases. In the first phase of the pipeline, researcher names from the FRIS database are matched with mentions in a subset of Belga.Press articles. If a name of a researcher is found, the coreference resolution is initiated. However, before resolving all coreferences, the positive article is translated from Dutch to English using the googletrans library. This translation step is crucial as the coreference resolution library used later in the pipeline—'fastcoref'—performs better with English text.

Retrieve research topics

The second stage involves fetching information about the research topics or expertise of the matched researchers using data from OpenAlex. A second filter is applied: researchers listed in FRIS, found in the Belga.Press articles yet not found in the OpenAlex database, are dumped. These names were dumped for the pipeline requires topics as only found in OpenAlex (see 'Scoring Topic Similarity'). Only those names that do appear in both FRIS and OpenAlex and are matched in a Belga.Press article are kept for further analysis. For the remaining researchers of that list, topics for those researchers are pulled from OpenAlex. If identical names are listed, e.g. 'John Smiths', all topics for each 'John Smith' is retrieved.

Coreference extraction

To assess whether the mentioned researcher is mentioned in relation with his or her research, one needs to establish the context in which the researcher is being mentioned in the mainstream media article. We deduce the context by deploying the OpenAlex topic model onto the sentences in which the researcher is mentioned in the mainstream media article. Extracting the sentences in which the researchers is mentioned is done using a ‘coreference’ library. Coreferences are those expressions in sentences that refer to the same named entity (e.g. John Smith, he, ‘his’ research). Coreference resolution than is resolving each occurrence of the referenced entity, extracting all sentences with the referenced entity.

In other words, to define whether the researcher is mentioned for non-academic interests or whether the mention is related to his field of expertise, we extracted the sentences in which the researcher was mentioned using a python library ‘fastcoref’ and extract the topic of that mainstream media article using the OpenAlex classifier. The assumption here is that the expertise or research of the researcher is mentioned, OpenAlex will be able to classify the mention using a label that is close to the labels associated with the researcher in OpenAlex itself.

However, coreference of the researcher alone (here dubbed as ‘coref level 1’) sometimes will not provide sufficient context. An example would be: ‘John Smith organizes a conference in Brussels. The conference is about biogenetics in the macaque monkey.’ To avoid too little context, we assume that the sentence in which the researcher is relevant to its mention and add the coreference cluster. In our example this would result in the coreference resolution for ‘John Smith’ (cf. John Smith organizes a conference in Brussels.) and the coreference cluster for ‘a conference’ and ‘Brussel’ (cf. The conference is about biogenetics in the macaque monkey.’). The final coref array will include ‘coref level 1’ and coref level 2’. Again, the assumption here is that all ‘other’ entities appearing in a sentence of the ‘coref level 1’ inadvertently are related to the topic in which the researcher is being mentioned.

This coreference array is then classified using the OpenAlex topic model resulting in predictions of topics of the mainstream media article. A final fallback in the pipeline is where neither coreference levels 1 nor 2 yield sufficient characters (e.g. ‘core level 1’ resulting in ‘Written by John Smith’). To capture these exceptions, the pipeline applies a classifier to determine if the article might be authored by the researcher, is summarized and fed into the OpenAlex model.

Scoring topic similarity

Once the ‘coreference array’ is defined, the fourth stage applies similarity analysis comparing topics extracted from OpenAlex with topics from the coreference-resolved arrays. If these are ‘closely’ related to each other, the mention is finally labelled as a positive. If not, the mention is labelled as a negative. To assign a similarity score, we use the tree structure of the OpenAlex topic models. The OpenAlex topics (cf. ‘topic level 1’) are grouped into subfields (‘topic level 2’) which are grouped in fields (cf. ‘topic level 3’) and finally grouped in domains (cf. ‘topic level 4’). Each topic therefore is part of a subfield, field and domain.

Scoring is as follows:

- if a ‘topic level 1’ of the mainstream media article AND that topic is also associated with the researcher, it gets the score of ‘1’ being a very granular match meaning that the mention mainstream media article is very close to his or her research
- if a match is found for ‘topic level 2’ (cf. a ‘subfield’), it is assigned the score 0.75, meaning that is closely related but less than those with a ‘topic level 1’
- if a match is found for ‘topic level 3’ (cf. ‘field’), it scores 0.5, which signifies that it is closer to their expertise than their specific research endeavours

- if a match is found for topic level 4', the score is 0.25, indicating that the mention is about their general expertise (e.g. an expertise on 'life sciences' and has little to do with specific research activities)
- if there is no match found for either of the levels, the mention is scored '0', indicating that the mention is nor about their research nor about their (academic) expertise.

In the case of multiple matches for different researchers holding the same name (e.g. common names such as 'John Smith'), the highest score is counted as the most probable match and assigned to the unique ID of both FRIS and OpenAlex. If multiple matches have an identical scoring, e.g. in the case where there are two John Smiths with a scoring of 0.5, the script raises a warning for a manual check.

Scoring evaluation

The evaluation of the scoring requires a close reading of the mainstream media article, manually fetch all names of potential researchers, a manual check whether the 'coreference array' retained sufficient information for the OpenAlex classifier to assign a correct label, and a manual check if the classifier assigned a correct label to the coreference array. Given the time-consuming close reading of the articles of both negatives and positives, as of writing the article a manual check was executed on 100 randomly selected positive articles, and 100 randomly selected negative articles.

Due to the scale of the scan, our team is moving the scripts to a more powerful GPU environment, in which we will scan all 4 million articles. For these intermediate results, a total of 2554 articles was processed, for which we scanned a total of 217.608 researchers as found in FRIS. A total of 722 researchers was found in the mainstream media articles, out of which 627 researchers were matched with their OpenAlex ID. A manual check revealed less than 0.1 error rate for the coreference extraction (cf. incorrect or not relevant sentences).

Preliminary manual checks indicate over 0.9 of the resolutions provided sufficient information for the model to process. Sufficient information is defined as sufficient information extracted from the mainstream media article allowing the OpenAlex classifier to label the article with a topic. To evaluate the scoring, we used the highest score, manually checked the accuracy of the label for the given mainstream article. A preliminary manual check of the accuracy of labelling was executed on more than 100 articles and was found very accurate (cf. < 0.8), showing that the OpenAlex model is apt classifying excerpts from mainstream media articles. We found a weak decrease in accuracy for those articles with multiple researchers.

Conclusion

The study successfully demonstrates the possibility to systematically integrate, weigh and analyse mainstream media mentions within the framework of scientometric and bibliometric analyses. It successfully (1) retrieves mentions of researchers in mainstream media articles and extract sufficient information, (2) evaluates whether the mention is related to academic research. Additionally, it allows to predict (3) whether the mention is either directly related to specific research or more general about the expertise of the researcher. Furthermore, it allows to back trace every step of the harvesting process (4) enabling provenance of each step in the prediction.

This opens a new window of integrating these mentions in (academic) repositories, weigh or evaluate the impact of the researcher and/or academic domains within mainstream media, given a full transparent labelling and evaluation process. Finally, given that all names are directly linked to specific researchers, the pipeline potentially initiates feeding these automated harvesting into institutional repositories for researchers to claim these mentions as part of their academic activities. To our knowledge, this is a first when it comes to automatically harvest mainstream media mentions that can be directly linked to researchers

and therefore integrates well with the push towards the inclusion of grey literature in institutional repositories.

Further research can refine the information retrieval using named entity retrieval in combination with relation extraction.

Limitations of the research

The study analyses only a subset of media articles from the Belga.press database, selectively sourced based on a lexicon. This does not capture the full spectrum of media mentions. However, the data set is not domain biased though due to its lexical filtering will likely contain significantly more mentions of researchers than found in the full data set of Belga.Press. Relying on a static snapshot from the FRIS database limits the ability to include ongoing updates in the FRIS researchers list. Implementing a dynamic data retrieval system could enhance the accuracy and relevance of research findings. For the purpose of a proof of concept, this limitation will have limited impact. On the other hand, the research methodology heavily depends on the accuracy of the FRIS database. Therefore inaccuracies within FRIS heavily impacts the outcomes, emphasizing the need for accurate (open) data sources.

Moreover, the study did not include searches for academic institutions, focusing solely on individual researchers. This limitation narrows the research scope, as it does not capture all research-related mentions in mainstream media that may be linked to institutional activities or achievements. Additionally, the reliance on string-based search techniques for identifying researchers in media articles may overlook misspellings or variant spellings of names, although such errors are expected to be minimal in this specific dataset.

Open science practices

This paper extensively engages with the principles of open science. Firstly, it utilizes the OpenAlex topic classification model, which is openly and freely available, exemplifying the paper's commitment to using accessible scientific tools. Secondly, it uses (and limits itself) to data as found in the freely accessible FRIS database. The result is the potential extension and direct link to these open data sets, both FRIS and OpenAlex, with grey literature observations. Furthermore, the study can be linked with the data from OpenAlex and therefore with the CWTS Leiden Ranking Open Edition generating greater integration of open datasets in research evaluation. Additionally, the research pipeline developed for this study will be released under an MIT license, promoting transparency, and encouraging reuse and adaptation. Finally, this paper ensures transparent provenance for mentions of grey literature, maintaining rigorous standards for data transparency and reliability, contributing significantly to the advancement of open science practices.

Author contributions

Following the credit.niso.org:

Dirk Derom: conceptualization (ID: 8b73531f-db56-4914-9502-4cc4d4d8ed73), Writing – original draft (ID: 43ebbd94-98b4-42f1-866b-c930cef228ca), Writing – review & editing (ID: d3aead86-f2a2-47f7-bb99-79de6421164d), Software (ID: f89c5233-01b0-4778-93e9-cc7d107aa2c8), Data curation (ID: f93e0f44-f2a4-4ea1-824a-4e0853b05c9d), Supervision (ID: 0c8ca7d4-06ad-4527-9cea-a8801fcb8746)

Padin Fazelian: Software (ID: f89c5233-01b0-4778-93e9-cc7d107aa2c8), Data curation (ID: f93e0f44-f2a4-4ea1-824a-4e0853b05c9d), conceptualization (ID: 8b73531f-db56-4914-9502-4cc4d4d8ed73)

Walter Ysebaert: conceptualization (ID: 8b73531f-db56-4914-9502-4cc4d4d8ed73), Supervision (ID: 0c8ca7d4-06ad-4527-9cea-a8801fcb8746), Funding acquisition (ID: 34ff6d68-132f-4438-a1f4-fba61ccf364a)

Competing interests

The authors may also use this section to declare that they have no competing interests.

References

- Anderson, P. S., Odom, A. R., Gray, H. M., Jones, J. B., Christensen, W. F., Hollingshead, T., Hadfield, J. G., Evans-Pickett, A., Frost, M., Wilson, C., Davidson, L. E., & Seeley, M. K. (2020). A case study exploring associations between popular media attention of scientific research and scientific citations. *PLoS ONE*, *15*(7), e0234912. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0234912>
- Bickley, M., Kousha, K., & Thelwall, M. (2022). A systematic method for identifying references to academic research in grey literature. *SCIENTOMETRICS*, *127*(12), 6913–6933. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-022-04408-4>
- Bickley, M. S., Kousha, K., & Thelwall, M. (2020). Can the impact of grey literature be assessed? An investigation of UK government publications cited by articles and books. *Scientometrics*, *125*(2), 1425–1444. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-020-03628-w>
- Cooper, K., Marsolek, W., Riegelman, A., Farrell, S., & Kelly, J. (2019). Grey Literature: Use, Creation, and Citation Habits of Faculty Researchers across Disciplines. *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication*, *7*(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.2314>
- Fahy, D. (2015). *The New Celebrity Scientists: Out of the Lab and Into the Limelight*. Rowman & Littlefield.
- Federico, M., Bertoldi, N., & Sandrini, V. (2003). *Bootstrapping Named Entity Recognition for Italian Broadcast News*. <https://doi.org/10.3115/1118693.1118731>
- Gelfand, J. (2005). “Knock, Knock:”—Are institutional repositories a home for grey literature? In D. J. Farace (Ed.), *GL6: Work on Grey in Progress, Conference Proceedings* (pp. 10–15). Textrelease. <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:000230446900002>
- Gul, S., Shah, T. A., Ahmad, S., Gulzar, F., & Shabir, T. (2020). Is grey literature really grey or a hidden glory to showcase the sleeping beauty. *Collection and Curation*, *40*(3), 100–111. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CC-10-2019-0036>
- Hovden, R. (2013). Bibliometrics for Internet media: Applying the h-index to YouTube. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, *64*(11), 2326–2331.
- Imran, M. K., Iqbal, S. M. J., Aslam, U., & Fatima, T. (2019). Does social media promote knowledge exchange? A qualitative insight. *MANAGEMENT DECISION*, *57*(3), 688–702. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MD-05-2017-0477>
- Jonker, H., Vanlee, F., & Ysebaert, W. (2022). Societal impact of university research in the written press: Media attention in the context of SIUR and the open science agenda among social scientists in Flanders, Belgium. *Scientometrics*, *127*(12), 7289–7306. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-022-04374-x>
- Joubert, M., & Weingart, P. (2019). The conflation of motives of science communication—Causes, consequences, remedies. *Journal of Science Communication*, *18*(03), Y01. <https://doi.org/10.22323/2.18030401>
- Lambert, S., Matthews, B. M., & Jones, C. (2006). Grey Literature, institutional repositories, and the organisational context. In D. J. Farace & J. Frantzen (Eds.), *SEVENTH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON GREY LITERATURE, GL7 CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS* (Issue 7, pp. 142–146). Textrelease. <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:000263992500019>

- Leidecker-Sandmann, M., Koppers, L., & Lehmkuhl, M. (2023). Correlations between the selection of topics by news media and scientific journals. *PLoS ONE*, *18*(1), e0280016. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0280016>
- McDevitt, M. (2022). Social Control of Intellect: Four Features of the Academic-Media Nexus. *COMMUNICATION THEORY*, *32*(3), 407–428. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ct/qtab015>
- Medina, L. R. (2023). The circulation of knowledge beyond the academia: On scholarly couplers at porous borders. *SOCIOLOGY COMPASS*, *17*(10). <https://doi.org/10.1111/soc4.13119>
- Moorhead, L. L., Fleerackers, A., & Maggio, L. (2023). “It’s my job”: A qualitative study of the mediatization of science within the scientist-journalist relationship. *JCOM-JOURNAL OF SCIENCE COMMUNICATION*, *22*(4), A05. <https://doi.org/10.22323/2.22040205>
- Myohanen, L., Taylor, E., & Keith, L. (2005). Accessing grey literature in public health: New York academy of medicine’s grey literature report. In D. J. Farace (Ed.), *GL6: Work on Grey in Progress, Conference Proceedings* (pp. 123–127). Textrelease. <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:000230446900019>
- Olesk, A. (2021). The types of visible scientists. *JCOM-JOURNAL OF SCIENCE COMMUNICATION*, *20*(2), A06. <https://doi.org/10.22323/2.20020206>
- Ravenscroft, J., Clare, A., & Liakata, M. (2018). HarriGT: A Tool for Linking News to Science. In F. Liu & T. Solorio (Eds.), *Proceedings of ACL 2018, System Demonstrations* (pp. 19–24). Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/P18-4004>
- Schoepfel, J., Le Bescond, I., & Prost, H. (2012). Open Is Not Enough Grey Literature in Institutional Repositories. In D. J. Farace & J. Frantzen (Eds.), *GREY CIRCUIT: FROM SOCIAL NETWORKING TO WEALTH CREATION* (Vol. 13, pp. 75-+). Textrelease. <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:000335704600008>
- Schoepfel, J., & Stock, C. (2008). Grey literature in French Digital Repositories: A Survey. In D. J. Farace (Ed.), *DESIGNING THE GREY GRID FOR INFORMATION SOCIETY* (Issue 10, pp. 39-+). Textrelease. <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:000264705400004>
- Schöpfel, J. (2019). Grey Literature and Professional Knowledge Making. In L. Börjesson & I. Huvila (Eds.), *Research Outside The Academy: Professional Knowledge-Making in the Digital Age* (pp. 137–153). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-94177-6_8
- Wang, J., & Yu, B. (2021). News2PubMed: A Browser Extension for Linking Health News to Medical Literature. *SIGIR '21 - PROCEEDINGS OF THE 44TH INTERNATIONAL ACM SIGIR CONFERENCE ON RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT IN INFORMATION RETRIEVAL*, 2605–2609. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3404835.3462788>
- Wani, J., & Ganaie, S. (2022). The scientific outcome in the domain of grey literature: Bibliometric mapping and visualisation using the R-bibliometrix package and the VOSviewer. *Library Hi Tech*, *42*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHT-01-2022-0012>